

Studies in Acetyl Bromide as a Polar Solvent. Part III. Formation of Acid/base Neutralisation Complexes in Acetyl Bromide

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Antimony tribromide, stannic bromide, and titanium tetrabromide, which act as solvo-acids in acetyl bromide, react with the ansolvo-bases (tetramethylammonium bromide, tetraethylammonium bromide, triethylbenzylammonium bromide, and dimethylethylphenylammonium bromide) and solvo-bases (quinoline, α -picoline, and dimethylaniline) to yield acid/base neutralisation complexes in acetyl bromide. The constitution of acidic and basic solutions in acetyl bromide has been discussed and the mode of formation of the acid/base neutralisation complexes, which have been isolated and analysed, indicated.

In the present investigations relating to the study of polar properties of acetyl bromide, complex compounds formed by the interaction of solvo-acids and solvo- and ansolvo-bases have been described. Acetyl bromide providing conducting solutions, when the Lewis acids, bases, and quaternary ammonium bromides are dissolved in it (Part I, this issue, p. 81), is indeed interesting so far its ionisation and the mode of ionisation of various substances in its solutions are concerned. The Lewis acids, antimony tribromide and stannic bromide, on dissolution increase conductance of acetyl bromide, which is due to the formation of solvo-acids, and their subsequent ionisation in solution. The mode of ionisation of solvo-acids, based on the conductance of their solutions in acetyl bromide and their behaviour in other solvents, may be expressed as :

In the present work only two upper stages of the ionisation have been realised and there is no indication of existence of the last stage.

On analogous grounds behaviour of titanium tetrabromide may be anticipated to be as :

The quaternary ammonium bromides, such as tetraethylammonium bromide, triethylbenzylammonium bromide, etc., also considerably enhance conductance of acetyl bromide and are expected to act as ansolvo-bases (Part I, *loc. cit.*). The mode of their ionisation may be exemplified by that of tetraethylammonium bromide as :

Organic tertiary bases, such as, α -picoline, quinoline, and dimethylaniline, also furnish solutions in acetyl bromide, which are more conducting than the pure solvent (Part I, *loc. cit.*).

This is interpreted to be due to ionisation of the solvo-bases formed. Actually, solvates of quite a few bases with acetyl bromide have already been isolated (Part I). Conductance of their solutions can only be due to their ionisation, which, keeping in view the strong electron-donor properties of nitrogen in the tertiary bases, can be represented as :

Antimony tribromide, dissolved in acetyl bromide, reacts with quaternary ammonium bromides to yield complexes of the type, R' R'' R''' R'''' N.SbBr₃.

Tetramethylammonium bromide is, however, an exception and formation of a compound of the formula [(CH₃)₄N]₂(CH₃CO).SbBr₆ takes place. This complex is obtained from triacetylum hexabromoantimonite as :

A similar compound has been encountered in the study of conductometric titrations between tetraethylammonium bromide and antimony tribromide in acetyl bromide (Part IV, this *issue*, p. 93). The compounds of antimony tribromide with other quaternary ammonium bromides are shown in Table I.

α -Picoline, quinoline, and dimethylaniline react with antimony tribromide in acetyl bromide to yield compounds of the general type (B.CH₃CO)SbBr₄. Formation of the typical compound between antimony tribromide and α -picoline in acetyl bromide may be interpreted on the basis of ionic species as :

The formation of feebly dissociated molecule of the solvent helps the reaction to completion.

Stannic bromide, which has been used as a dibasic solvo-acid in arsenic tribromide (Jander and Gunther, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1958, **297**, 81 ; 1959, **298**, 241), reacts with quaternary ammonium bromides in acetyl bromide to yield compounds of the general formula :

Its formation can be represented by a reaction between tetraethylammonium bromide and stannic bromide in acetyl bromide as :

Quinoline and diethylaniline, which form monoacid solvo-bases in acetyl bromide, react with stannic bromide to yield complexes of the general type (B.CH₃CO)₂SnBr₆. The mode of formation of these complexes may be represented as :

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TABLE I

* Complexes.	Formula.	Colour.	M.P.	%Metal Found. Calc.	%Bromine Found. Calc.	%Nitrogen Found. Calc.
Bis-tetraethyl Am acetylium HA	$[Me_2N]_2 \cdot Ac \cdot SbBr_6$	Yellow	325-40°	15.99 15.37	60.03 60.54	1.82 1.76
Tetraethyl-Am TA	$(Et_4N) \cdot SbBr_6$	"	212-15°	20.40 21.30	55.73 55.98	2.67 2.45
Dimethylethylphenyl-Am TA	$(Me)_2N \cdot Et \cdot Ph \cdot SbBr_6$	Light yellow	158-62°	19.07 20.05	53.04 53.07	2.46 2.36
Triethylbenzyl-Am TA	$Et_3N \cdot C_6H_5 \cdot SbBr_6$	Yellow	125-28°	19.62 19.21	49.37 50.49	2.46 2.21
Dimethylphenylbenzyl-Am TA	$Me_2N \cdot Ph \cdot C_6H_5 \cdot SbBr_6$	"	140-46°	18.92 18.63	48.99 48.94	2.48 2.14
Acetylquinolinium TA	$C_8H_7N \cdot Ac \cdot SbBr_6$	"	185-88°	20.50 19.85	52.64 52.14	1.99 2.27
Acetyl- α -picolinium TA	$C_8H_7N \cdot Ac \cdot SbBr_6$	"	92-112°	20.84 21.08	55.67 55.38	2.26 2.42
Acetyldimethylanilinium TA	$C_6H_{11}N \cdot Ac \cdot SbBr_6$	"	104-10°	20.98 20.11	52.43 52.82	2.37 2.31
Bis-tetramethyl-Am HS	$[Me_4N]_2 \cdot SnBr_6$	"	320°	14.40 15.89	64.91 64.19	3.42 3.75
Bis-tetraethyl-Am HS	$[Et_4N]_2 \cdot SnBr_6$	Light yellow	307°	13.97 13.82	55.49 55.89	3.06 3.26
Bis-dimethylethylphenyl-Am HS	$[Me_2N \cdot Et \cdot Ph]_2 \cdot SnBr_6$	Yellow	207°	13.40 13.21	52.68 53.41	3.01 3.12
Bis-triethylbenzyl-Am HS	$[Et_3N \cdot C_6H_5]_2 \cdot SnBr_6$	"	161-63°	12.16 12.08	48.57 48.84	3.03 2.85
Bis-dimethylphenylbenzyl-Am HS	$[Me_2N \cdot C_6H_5 \cdot C_6H_5]_2 \cdot SnBr_6$	Greenish yellow	172-85°	11.21 11.61	47.17 46.93	3.01 2.73
Bis-acetylquinolinium HS	$[C_8H_7N \cdot Ac]_2 \cdot SnBr_6$	Reddish pink	186-89°	12.96 12.59	50.09 50.50	2.63 2.97
Tri-acetyl- α -picolinium acetylium bis-HS	$[C_8H_7N \cdot Ac]_3 (Ac) (SnBr_6)_2$	Yellow	152-55°	14.37 14.40	58.25 58.24	2.31 2.54
Tri-acetyldimethylanilinium acetylium bis-HS hemi-acetyl bromide.	$(C_6H_{11}N \cdot Ac)_3 \cdot Ac (SnBr_6)_2 \cdot \frac{1}{2} AcBr$	Dirty yellow	145-48°	13.13 13.23	55.36 55.74	2.19 2.34
Bis-acetyldiethylanilinium HS	$[PhN \cdot Et_2]_2 \cdot Ac \cdot 2SnBr_6$	Light brown	..	12.14 12.05	48.99 48.85	2.73 2.85
Bis-tetramethyl-Am HT tetramethyl-Am bromide	$[Me_4N]_2 \cdot TiBr_6 \cdot 4Me_4NBr$	Brown	..	3.45 3.71	61.21 61.90
Bis-tetraethylammonium HT	$[Et_4N]_2 \cdot TiBr_6$	Red	..	6.11 6.09	59.22 60.91
Bis-dimethylethylphenyl-Am HT	$[Me_2N \cdot Et \cdot Ph]_2 \cdot TiBr_6$	"	..	4.87 5.79 10.00	49.61 57.94
Bis-triethylbenzyl-Am HT	$[Et_3N \cdot C_6H_5]_2 \cdot TiBr_6$	Black	..	4.90 5.26	51.98 52.63
Bis-dimethylphenylbenzyl-Am HT	$[Me_2N \cdot Ph \cdot C_6H_5]_2 \cdot TiBr_6$	Red	..	5.02 5.04	50.30 50.42

* Am denotes ammonium. HA & TA denote respectively hexa- and tetra-bromo-antimonite. HS & HT denote respectively hexabromo-stannate and-titanate.

α -Picoline and dimethylaniline, which also form monoacid solvo-bases in acetyl bromide, react with stannic bromide to form complexes of the general formula $(B.CH_3CO)_3CH_3CO.(SnBr_6)_2$. These complexes appear to be equimolecular mixtures of the normal complexes $(B.CH_3CO)_2SnBr_6$ and the acid complex $(B.CH_3CO)(CH_3CO).SnBr_6$. The possible formation of the acid salt can be expressed as :

Titanium tetrabromide forms unstable and deliquescent complexes with the quaternary ammonium bromides, which can be expressed by the general formula $(R' R'' R''' R'''' N)_2TiBr_6$.

Formation of these complexes may be explained on the basis of ionic species, which exist in solutions. For instance :

The complexes of organic tertiary bases with titanium tetrabromide are difficult to isolate as these are very much susceptible to moisture and decompose easily.

EXPERIMENTAL

Acetyl bromide, prepared from pure glacial acetic acid and phosphorus tribromide (Burton and Degering, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 227), was purified as described in preceding parts (*loc. cit.*).

Tetramethylammonium bromide, tetraethylammonium bromide, dimethylethylphenylammonium bromide, triethylbenzylammonium bromide, dimethylphenylbenzylammonium bromide, etc. were purified by crystallisation. These were analysed for bromide by Volhard's method in order to determine their percentage purity.

Quinoline, α -picoline, dimethylaniline, and diethylaniline were purified before use by refluxing them over KOH beads for about 2 hours in an all-glass apparatus, and finally distilling in an atmosphere of nitrogen. Titanium tetrabromide, stannic bromide, and antimony tribromide were purified by distillation in an all-glass apparatus.

General Procedure for Preparation of Acid/base Complexes

When the solutions of solvo-acids and solvo- or ansolvo-bases in acetyl bromide were mixed together, the acid/base neutralisation complexes were precipitated from the reaction mixture. Antimony complexes were precipitated by taking acids and bases in the ratio 1:1 in acetyl bromide. Stannic bromide reacted with bases in acetyl bromide in the ratio 1:2, resulting mostly in the formation of non-deliquescent, yellow complexes. Complexes of titanium tetrabromide with ansolvo-bases, such as tetraethylammonium bromide, etc., were isolated by mixing the components (acids and bases) in the ratio 1:2. All these complexes were filtered through a sintered glass funnel in a dry atmosphere and washed with dry benzene. These were kept under vacuum and analysed for bromine by Volhard's method. Titanium and tin were estimated as titanium dioxide and tin dioxide gravimetrically while antimony was determined iodimetrically. Nitrogen in the quaternary ammonium bromide complexes was analysed commercially while in the complexes of the Lewis acids with tertiary bases, nitrogen was determined by the Jackson and Smith method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 544).